

THE IMPORTANCE OF ENERGY USE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY

Irisboyev Farkhod Boymirzayevich

Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute.

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Abstract. Energy consumption will continue to increase the level of production increases while ensuring its growth. Economic development is physical and perfectly automatic based on controlled machines, only consumed energy and can only be accelerated by increasing the level of production.

Key words: Solar energy, chemical energy of fuel, use of gas and oil, chemical energy of organic fuel, nuclear energy, thermonuclear energy, geothermal energy, solar energy falling on the earth.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ЭНЕРГИИ В РАЗВИТИИ ОБЩЕСТВА

Аннотация. Потребление энергии будет продолжать увеличиваться по мере увеличения уровня производства при обеспечении его роста. Экономическое развитие является физическим и совершенно автоматическим, основанным на управляемых машинах, оно потребляет только энергию и может быть ускорено только за счет повышения уровня производства.

Ключевые слова: Солнечная энергия, химическая энергия топлива, использование газа и нефти, химическая энергия органического топлива, атомная энергия, термоядерная энергия, геотермальная энергия, солнечная энергия, падающая на землю.

The development of human society and its achievements is a direct result level of output and material conditions necessary for people's lives is related to creation. Scientific, technical and social progress in general increase in consumed energy, more new energy at the same time as mastering the use of effective types increases.

Modern cars consume a lot of energy is a large amount. Express this based on the following comparison possible All the working population of the world every year even if you work 8 hours a day with full physical strength which is produced in thermal and hydroelectric power stations cannot produce one hundredth of the energy. Energy consumption will continue to increase the level of production increases while ensuring its growth. Economic development is physical and perfectly automatic based on controlled machines, only consumed energy and can only be accelerated by increasing the level of production. The need for energy has continuously increased. This in turn search for new energy sources, energy other than one type created the need to develop new methods of species transformation.

At present, different types of energy are used - solar energy, organic chemical energy of fuels, rivers, seas and oceans mechanical energy of water, wind energy, heavy nuclei use of nuclear energy generated during its fission is traditional. Figure 1.1 shows the last 20 years of the 19th century and the 20th century in various aspects of human activity on a global scale during the century the dynamics of energy resource use is described. From him The use of all types of energy resources is increasing intensively we will observe that it has gone. In this case, the relative increase in the use of coal the progress is relatively even from year to year, at the end of the 20th

Century about 30% of the total used energy resources, the relative growth of gas and oil consumption has increased sharply we'll see if he's gone. The main reason for this is to transfer them to a distance and is that the use requires low costs.

Such intensive growth of the demand for energy search for new reserves of new energy resources, from them such as efficient use, identification of alternative energy sources requires the performance of tasks. All the energy available on the earth at the present time the potential of resources is in the following amounts in the conditional fuel unit evaluated (t.sh.yo.):

- chemical energy of organic fuel - $1.77 \cdot 10^{13}$;
- nuclear energy - $0.67 \cdot 10^{14}$;
- thermonuclear energy - $1.22 \cdot 10^{17}$;
- geothermal energy - $1.0 \cdot 10^{14}$;
- energy of the sun falling on the globe - $0.82 \cdot 10^{14}$;
- energy of rivers (one year) - $0.4 \cdot 10^{10}$;
- wind energy (one year) - $2.1 \cdot 10^{11}$;
- bioenergy of forests (one year) - $0.5 \cdot 10^{10}$;
- flow energy (one year) - $0.86 \cdot 10^{14}$.

The construction of the energy system and its working conditions are direct natural factors (for example, availability of water bodies, energy geographic location of resources and location of consumers) is related to The state of the biosphere, the work of its energy devices level of pollution related to the technical of the energy system

Social factors Biosphere Energy system with fuel provide system Energy consumption system 9 certain limitations regarding the characteristics and working conditions creates.

Management of the energy system is only about its impact on the biosphere not social functions of the fuel supply system, taking into account the influence of industry, transport and other factors is done. Energy has a negative impact on the environment and human health is one of the sources. Therefore, reduce its impact development and implementation of technologies in this field today It is one of the most urgent issues facing scientists and specialists. Energy is natural phenomena, culture and human life is the general basis. In addition, the movement of energy and matter is different is a quantitative indicator of their appearance. Energy by type chemical, mechanical, electrical, nuclear, etc. is divided into Man energy energy resources that can be used by exists in so-called material objects. All kinds of energy resources are very much in practical needs as the main energy resources with a large number of users is held. They include organic fuels such as coal, oil, gas, as well as rivers, seas and oceans, sun, wind, heat of the ground (geothermal) energies are included. Energy resources are renewable and non-renewable divided into types.

Continuously to renewable energy resources renewable energy resources (water, wind, etc.) is included. Advances in non-renewable energy resources in nature concentrated, but does not appear in the current geological conditions energy resources (for example, coal). Energy obtained directly from nature (fuel, water, wind, earth thermal energy, nuclear energy, etc.) primary energy, it appeared as a result of modification by man in special devices energy is called secondary energy.

In its name, power plants are user-primary represents the type of energy. For example, a thermal power plant (PPP) heat energy (primary energy) into electrical energy (secondary energy), as well as hydroelectric power station (GES) water energy into electricity, nuclear power plant (NPP) atom converts energy into electricity. Obtaining the required type of energy and consumers with it supply is carried out in the process of energy production. This the process can be divided into five stages.

1. Acquisition and concentration of energy resources: fuel mining and preparation, using hydrotechnical facilities create etc.

2. Transfer of energy resources to converting devices: this by conveying water, gas, etc. on land or water, or in pipes is done by driving.

3. Primary energy in secondary existing conditions to the type of energy that is convenient for distribution and consumption (usually to electrical and thermal energies) change.

4. Transmission and distribution of converted energy.

5. Consumption of energy in transmitted and modified forms to do If the energy of primary energy resources is used If we assume that it is 100%, then the useful work energy is only 35-40%, the rest is wasted. The bulk of the waste corresponds to thermal energy. Energy waste is the current energy determined by the technical characteristics of the machines. Different energy resources in the regions and countries of the Earth It is located in the suburbs. There are many places where they are available does not match with places to do. of oil reserves in the world more than half of them are located in the Near and Middle East regions consumption on the ground is 4-5 times higher than the world average is low.

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